

Characterisation of lipids present in waste matter of two fresh water fish, *Catla catla* and *Labio rohita*

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Abstract : The lipid content, fatty acid composition of the lipid, natural antioxidant content and physicochemical parameters of the lipid were analyzed for the waste matter (consisting of liver, intestine, mesentery and associate parts of digestive tract excluding bile sac and air bladder) obtained from two fresh water fish species, *Catla catla* and *Labio rohita* as a new lipid source rich in PUFA. The oil content was 23–25% (w/w) of total waste matter. The triglyceride fraction was the major lipid class (50–53%) with smaller proportions of polar and other non-polar lipids. Major sterol component of the lipid was cholesterol (5–7%). Oil obtained from the two fish wastes showed a significant amount of carotene which presumably prevents oxidation during extraction and storage of the extracted lipid. The content of saturated and monoenoic fatty acid was similar for both species, however, the *C. catla* waste oil had twice as much DHA and EPA than *L. rohita*. The n-3/n-6 fatty acid ratio was somewhat different with 1.82 for *C. catla* and 1.03 for *L. rohita*. The overall study suggests the possibility of future commercial utilization of waste matter lipids from both of these commonly used fresh water fish, an unconventional, cheap, and easily available source.

Keywords : Fish wastes, fish waste lipids, carotene, n-3 and n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids.

Introduction

Fish is an integral part of human diet. It is liked not only for its taste but also for its high nutritional value. Fish is high in protein and some varieties are also rich in good quality lipid containing essential fatty acids^{1,2}. Fish portions are prepared by sawing, which produces 3–6% of waste depending on the species. Fish filleting also leads to waste, which can amount to 50% of the total weight of the raw material. Most of the waste is composed of head, intestine, skin, bones, scales etc. Some of these waste parts of marine fishes particularly have high content of nutritive compounds like protein and lipid especially the intestine and its associate organs like liver, mesentery and digestive tract^{3,4} and these are also reported as sources of beneficial fatty acids viz. eicosapentaenoic (EPA) (20 : 5) and docosahexaenoic (DHA) (22 : 6)^{5,6}. These fatty acids have been reported to be important in preventing or reducing heart disease⁷, inflammatory disorders⁸. DHA

also acts as a nutritional supplement for the brain and retina development in babies⁹. The fish waste is also rich in valuable minerals, enzymes, pigments and flavours that are required by many industries including food, agriculture, aquaculture and pharmaceuticals^{10,11}. Researches about lipid and fatty acid composition of various liver oils of marine fishes have already been done but those studies were mainly on deep sea species^{5,6,10}. Considerably less information about this subject exists for fresh water fish species which are regularly cultivated and consumed by a huge number of people.

These waste materials are usually utilized for the production of fish meal and in a very few cases it is collected for the production of animal feeds; more frequently it is simply discarded³. Instead of rejecting, the strategic development to characterise and utilise these fresh water fish wastes may lead to feasible opportunity not only to add some value to these wastes but also to identify a

source of utilisable lipid either for edible or for non-edible purpose. The objective of the present study is to collect waste material (consisting of liver, intestine, mesentery and associate parts of digestive tract excluding bile sac and air bladder) samples of two widely consumed fish in India like *Catla catla* and *Labeo rohita* and characterize their waste materials with respect to lipid content, lipid classes, fatty acid profiles, and other physicochemical parameters.

Results and discussion

In this study liver, intestine, mesentery and associate parts of digestive tract excluding bile sac and air bladder of *C. catla* and *L. rohita* were considered as waste material. The quantity of waste material in *C. catla* and *L. rohita* species were 6.0 ± 0.6 g/100 g and 5.3 ± 1.4 g/100 g of total weight of the fish respectively (Table 1). Total lipid content of waste materials were 23.05 ± 9.0 g/100 g (w/w) in *C. catla* and 25.5 ± 17 g/100 g (w/w) in *L. rohita* (Table 1). Results showed that the waste lipid yield of both the species is much higher than 8 g/100 g and can be considered as a high fat fish product¹. Moreover, the lipid content of waste of *C. catla* and *L. rohita* is much higher than cod offal, herring and sardine fish

waste^{5,12,13} and can be counted as being a good source of lipid.

As a part of physicochemical property determination, RI, slip melting point and viscosity of the oils were determined along with the saponification number and iodine value. Refractive indices of the oils (1.368 ± 0.001 in *C. catla*, 1.235 ± 0.001 in *L. rohita*) showed no significant differences among species (Table 2). Saponification values (207.68 ± 2.71 in *C. catla* and 208.77 ± 2.45 in *L. rohita*) of both oils were also quite similar but iodine value for *C. catla* (101.51 ± 0.21) was significantly lower than *L. rohita* (110.67 ± 0.34) (Table 2), reflecting the lower unsaturation present in the *C. catla* waste lipid. The viscosity of the two lipids is also given in Table 2 and the values showed a great difference with each other (143.6 ± 2.55 for *C. catla* and 92.3 ± 3.05 for *L. rohita*). Slip melting point of *C. catla* (32.7 ± 0.21 °C) was little higher than *L. rohita* (31.0 ± 0.14 °C).

The fish are not able to synthesize carotene but can accumulate it from their food¹⁴. The carotenes are stored in the liver¹⁵ and due to their lipid-soluble nature, are extracted with the oil. The carotene content of the fish waste lipid was high in *C. catla* (69.11 ± 13.55 µg/g lipid) but it was quite low in *L. rohita* (34.87 ± 8.51 µg/g lipid) (Table 2). Carotene is the most effective natural antioxidant¹⁶; therefore it may protect the lipid from oxidation as well as from the *in vivo* peroxidation of the organism that consume them.

The lipid component (polar and non-polar) of fish wastes are shown in Table 3. Triglyceride (TAG) was the major lipid class; 53.2 ± 9.9 g/100 g and 50.8 ± 10.3 g/100 g of lipid of *C. catla* and *L. rohita* respectively. TAG is the main energy source for the fish and it is mainly stored in the liver and is mobilized in tendency of the metabolic necessities of fish. The predominance of

Table 1. Waste content of the fish samples and lipid and moisture content of the fish waste

Name of species	Waste percentage ^a (w/w)	Moisture content (g/100 g sample)	Amount of lipid present in wet tissue (g/100 g sample)
<i>Catla catla</i>	6.0 ± 0.6	44.5 ± 17.6	23.0 ± 5.9
<i>Labeo rohita</i>	5.3 ± 1.3	48.9 ± 28.2	25.5 ± 17.2

^aWaste weight as a percentage of the whole body weight.

Values are Mean \pm S.D.

Mean values of six samples with three replications.

Table 2. Physicochemical parameters and carotene content of fish waste lipids

Name of species	Saponification value	Iodine value	Refractive index (at 33 °C)	Slip melting point (°C)	Viscosity (cP) (at 33 °C)	Carotene content (µg/g lipid)
<i>Catla catla</i>	207.68 ± 2.71	101.51 ± 0.21	1.45 ± 0.01	32.7 ± 0.21	143.6 ± 2.55	69.11 ± 13.55
<i>Labeo rohita</i>	208.77 ± 2.45	110.67 ± 0.34^a	1.46 ± 0.01	31.2 ± 0.34^a	92.3 ± 3.05	34.87 ± 8.51^a

Values are Mean \pm S.D.

Mean values of six samples with three replications.

^aValues are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different between *Catla catla* and *Labeo rohita*.

Table 3. Lipid class composition of the two fish waste lipids

Name of species	TAG (g/100 g lipid)	DAG (g/100 g lipid)	MAG (g/100 g lipid)	FFA (g/100 g lipid)	Phospholipid (g/100 g lipid)	Others* (g/100 g lipid)
<i>Catla catla</i>	53.2±9.9	6.9±1.3	5.3±1.8	14.7±2.5	0.6±0.2	14.9±4.2
<i>Labeo rohita</i>	50.8±10.3	9.9±3.6	7.0±2.0	5.0±2.1 ^a	0.3±0.1	23.2±6.3

Values are Mean ±S.D.

Mean values of six samples with three replications.

TAG - Triacylglycerol; DAG - Diacylglycerol; MAG - Monoacylglycerol; FFA - Free Fatty Acid.

*Others include pigment, hydrocarbon, sterol, sterol ester etc.

^aValues are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different between *Catla catla* and *Labeo rohita*.

TAG over the rest of the lipid components has also been reported in liver oil of other ray *Dasyatis bleekeri*⁴. The amounts of phospholipid present in two fish waste lipids were 0.6 ± 0.2 g/100 g and 0.3 ± 0.1 g/100 g of lipid obtained from the waste of *C. catla* and *L. rohita* respectively (Table 3). The phospholipids are contributed mainly by the cell membranes as this is considered as building bricks of cell membrane. Increase in neutral storage lipids result in reduction in proportion of polar lipid, particularly phospholipid¹⁷. The FFA present in the waste lipid of *C. catla* (14.7 ± 2.5 g/100 g of lipid) was quite high due to the presence of fish liver in the waste matter and lipids are very prone to lypophilic enzymatic activity which counting for high free fatty acids, as in the case cod liver oil (12.6 g/100 g of lipid)¹⁸. Higher concentration of free fatty acids is not desirable for oil used for edible application but according to Ackman *et al.* free fatty acid present in fish oil is not mentionworthy as these fatty acids are readily digestible and provide satisfactory nutritional compatibility with TAG¹. So the higher amount of free fatty acid present in waste lipid of *C. catla* can be ignored in nutritional point of view.

The sterols participate in the synthesis of vitamin D, sexual hormones, bile acid and in absorption and transport of fatty acids. Total sterol present in *C. catla* and *L. rohita* was significantly different (8.5 ± 3.4 g/100 g and 6.5 ± 2.7 g/100 g of total lipid in *C. catla* and *L. rohita* respectively) (Table 4). The content of free sterol is mainly composed of cholesterol; 7.0 ± 0.7 g/100 g of total lipid in *C. catla* and 5.4 ± 0.2 g/100 g of total lipid in *L. rohita* (Table 4). These observations suggest that among all the sterols, cholesterol has the best structural function in membranes and this observation also complies with the study done by Nes¹⁹. 4.2 ± 2.7 g/100

Table 4. Total sterol, sterol esters and cholesterol content of two fish waste lipids

Name of species	Total sterol (g/100 g lipid)	Sterol ester (g/100 g lipid)	Cholesterol (g/100 g lipid)
<i>Catla catla</i>	8.5 ± 3.4	nd	7.0 ± 0.7
<i>Labeo rohita</i>	6.5 ± 2.2	4.2 ± 2.7^a	5.4 ± 0.2^a

Values are mean ±S.D.

Mean values of six samples with three replications.

nd - not detected.

^aValues are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different between *Catla catla* and *Labeo rohita*.

g sterol esters was present in waste lipid of *L. rohita* but that was absent in *C. catla* (Table 4).

The fatty acid compositions of the fish waste lipids are shown in Table 5. The total content of saturated fatty acid (SFA) of *C. catla* and *L. rohita* were determined as 29.98 ± 7.49 g/100 g and 28.14 ± 3.34 g/100 g respectively. The predominant SFAs in all the samples were palmitic (C16 : 0) it was 21.95 ± 5.2 g/100 g for *C. catla* and 20.98 ± 3.06 g/100 g for *L. rohita*.

The unsaturated fatty acids were the major fraction in the waste matter lipid of the two carp species studied (Table 5). The monoenoic fatty acids (MUFA) content were similar in both species (43.6 ± 5.54 g/100 g in *C. catla* and 43.02 ± 6.40 g/100 g in *L. rohita*). Among the monoenoic fatty acids, oleic (18 : 1) (24.01 ± 4.46 g/100 g in *C. catla* and 25.05 ± 9.37 g/100 g in *L. rohita*) and palmitoleic (16 : 1) (12.39 ± 2.61 g/100 g in *C. catla* and 10.73 ± 5.32 g/100 g in *L. rohita*) were present in higher concentrations.

The total polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA) content of fish waste lipid was determined to be 21.68 ± 3.89 g/100 g in *C. catla* and 23.65 ± 2.58 g/100 g in *L. rohita*.

Table 5. Total fatty acid composition of the two fish waste lipids

Fatty acids	Amount (g/100 g)	
	<i>Catla catla</i>	<i>Labeo rohita</i>
14 : 0	2.18 ± 0.93	2.24 ± 0.71
14 : 1	0.90 ± 0.46	0.68 ± 0.16
16 : 0	21.95 ± 5.20	20.98 ± 3.06
16 : 1 n-7	12.39 ± 2.60	10.73 ± 5.32
16 : 1 n-9	3.29 ± 2.23	2.02 ± 0.79 ^a
16 : 2	1.13 ± 0.71	1.18 ± 0.38
18 : 0	4.85 ± 1.46	3.80 ± 1.43
18 : 1	24.01 ± 4.46	25.05 ± 9.37
18 : 2	4.59 ± 2.66	8.83 ± 2.98 ^a
18 : 3	3.51 ± 0.79	5.15 ± 2.48
18 : 4	0.40 ± 0.33	0.66 ± 0.55
20 : 0	0.22 ± 0.19	nd ^a
20 : 1	1.40 ± 1.05	1.66 ± 0.87
20 : 3	nd	0.89 ± 0.42 ^a
20 : 4	2.77 ± 1.23	2.04 ± 0.61
20 : 5	3.89 ± 2.22	1.99 ± 1.34
22 : 1	nd	1.15 ± 0.86 ^a
22 : 1 n-11	0.89 ± 0.74	0.68 ± 0.52
22 : 5	0.79 ± 0.23	0.44 ± 0.37
24 : 0	1.37 ± 0.47	1.12 ± 0.56
22 : 6	4.60 ± 1.29	2.47 ± 1.32
24 : 1	0.72 ± 0.55	1.04 ± 0.93
Others	4.16 ± 1.73	5.19 ± 1.26
SFA	29.98 ± 7.49	28.14 ± 3.34
MUFA	43.60 ± 5.54	43.02 ± 6.40
PUFA	19.62 ± 3.71	23.65 ± 2.58
n-3/n-6	1.82 ± 0.51	1.03 ± 0.44

Values are Mean ± S.D.

Mean values of six samples with three replications.

^aValues are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different between *Catla catla* and *Labeo rohita*.

Total PUFA was mainly composed of n-3 and n-6 fatty acids. The high concentration of n-3 PUFA in waste lipid of *C. catla* fish was EPA (C20 : 5) (3.89 ± 2.22 g/100 g) and DHA (C22 : 6) (4.6 ± 1.29 g/100 g) which established the biomedical importance of this fish waste lipid. The concentrations of EPA (1.99 ± 1.34 g/100 g) and DHA (2.47 ± 1.32 g/100 g) were low in *L. rohita*. Total amount of EPA and DHA of these fish waste lipid was low in comparison to marine fish liver oil but comparable with the other Indian Puffer liver lipid²⁰. The amount of alpha linolenic acid (C18 : 3 n-3) was 3.51 ± 0.79 g/100 g in *C. catla* but it was higher in *L. rohita* (5.15 ± 2.48

g/100 g). The n-6 arachidonic acid (n-6, C20 : 4) plays an important role on the growth of human body and is a precursor of prostaglandin and thromboxane²¹. The arachidonic acid was found in both the lipids and the content was not much different with each other (2.77 ± 1.23 g/100 g in *C. catla*, 2.04 ± 0.61 g/100 g in *L. rohita*) and comparable with lipid from liver of Sardine⁵. Amount of another n-6 PUFA, linoleic (C18 : 2) acid in *L. rohita* was quite high compared to *C. catla* (and 4.59 ± 2.66 g/100 g in *C. catla* and 8.83 ± 2.48 g/100 g in *L. rohita*). The ratio of n-3 and n-6 fatty acids is a useful index to evaluate the nutritional value of a lipid due to their beneficial effects on human health especially on coronary heart diseases, cancer and autoimmune diseases and a 1 : 1 ratio has the best beneficial effect on health²². Both the species had good n-3/n-6 ratios (1.82 ± 0.51 for *C. catla* and 1.03 ± 0.44 for *L. rohita*), making them suitable for human or aquaculture use.

In spite of the beneficial effects that fish consumption, fish can harbor a number of biological and chemical hazards, such as toxic compounds, pathogenic bacteria and viruses, which can survive the processing steps. Unfortunately the chemical contaminants are stored within the lipid component of the fish²³ so they are well protected when entering the human body. Therefore fish oils should be tested at least for toxic metal contamination such as mercury and arsenic. Results showed that total mercury concentration was below 0.1 mg/kg in both *C. catla* and *L. rohita* which were much lower than the regulatory limit 0.5 mg Hg/kg and total arsenic concentrations in *C. catla* and *L. rohita* were found 2.6 ± 0.35 and 3.95 ± 0.20 mg As kg⁻¹ (Table 6). There are very few reports on arsenic contamination in fish lipid and it shows that total arsenic concentrations in the various fish oils ranged

Table 6. Total mercury and arsenic content of two fish waste lipids

Name of species	Mercury (mg/kg lipid)	Arsenic (mg/kg lipid)
Permissible limit	0.5 mg Hg/kg	6 mg As/kg
<i>Catla catla</i>	<0.1	2.6 ± 0.35
<i>Labeo rohita</i>	<0.1	3.95 ± 0.20^a

Values are Mean ± S.D.

Mean values of six samples with three replications.

^aValues are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different between *Catla catla* and *Labeo rohita*.

from 4.3–10.5 mg As kg⁻¹ 24. In most fish samples, however, arsenic is present primarily as organoarsenic compounds and greater than 90% of the arsenic found in marine fish is present as arsenobetaine, which is considered non-toxic. While the fate of organic arsenicals has not been clearly defined in man, arsenobetaine from sea-food is known to be readily absorbed (75–85% bioavailability) and rapidly excreted. The maximum level of total arsenic in fish feed is 6 mg/kg (EU) and the levels of total arsenic in the study samples were much lower than the regulatory limit of 2 µg/g (wet wt) and hence are safe for consumption²⁵.

Experimental

Sample collection :

Six samples of each *C. catla* and *L. rohita* (2–3 kg average weight) were collected from river Ganges of West Bengal throughout the year of 2009. Fishes were dissected immediately and the intestine part along with livers and other waste organs were collected and soaked on filter paper to remove surface moisture and weighed and stored at -20 °C, for no more than 2 weeks, until oil extraction. To avoid the seasonal variation, samples were collected through out the year and average data are presented.

All the reagents and standards used were procured from Merck India Ltd., Mumbai, India.

Methods :

Moisture content :

Moisture content was determined by drying fish waste samples in an air oven at 110 °C until a constant weight was obtained.

Lipid extraction :

Prior to lipid extraction, each waste sample was defrosted and homogenized for 2 min in a Warring blender homogenizer (type RQ-127A). Temperature during homogenization did not exceed 20 °C. The waste homogenates were immediately subjected to lipid extraction.

Lipid extraction was carried out following the extraction procedure outlined by McGill and Moffat (1992)²⁶. Anhydrous sodium sulphate (30%, w/w) was added to the waste homogenate, mixed for 3 min and centrifuged at 1150×g for 20 min at 25 °C. The resulting oil was

divided in 15 ml aliquots and stored at -20 °C in small glass vials under nitrogen atmosphere. This oil was used for the determination of lipid classes, carotenes and physicochemical parameters. Separately, to determine the total lipid content of waste matter, 1 g aliquots of homogenized waste were taken for total lipids content determination following the procedure described by Bligh and Dyer²⁷.

Physicochemical parameters of the oil :

The saponification number (SN), iodine value (IV), refractive index (RI) and Slip melting point were determined following the methodology given in the AOAC (1995)²⁸. Viscosity is determined by Brookfield viscometer [DV-II +Pro].

Carotenes :

The total carotene analysis in the oil was carried out according to Simpson and Haard²⁹. The accurately weighed oil samples were dissolved in 10 ml spectroscopic grade petroleum ether (40–60 °C) and the absorbance was measured at 468 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer [UV-1700 Pharma Spee, Make : Shimadzu Corporation Ltd.].

Identification and quantification of lipid class :

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of the lipid constituents present in fish oil were carried out by high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC)³⁰. A pre-coated TLC plates (20 × 20 cm) without fluorescent indicator containing silica gel 60 (0.25 mm thick) (Merck, Mumbai, India) were used for fractionation of triacylglycerols, diacylglycerols, monoacylglycerols, free fatty acids, fatty alcohol, sterol and hydrocarbon. The fish lipid sample (400 mg) was spotted over a width of 10 at 1 cm beneath the top of the plate. TLC was carried out at 25 °C in a glass tank (15 × 25 × 25 cm) using as the carrier agent a 90 : 10 : 0.5 mixtures of hexane, diethyl ether and acetic acid (v/v/v). Plates were developed by spraying a solution of 10% (w/v) phosphomolybdic acid in ethanol. Lipid constituents were identified by comparison of their *R_f* values with standards. The TLC plates were scanned in a Canmag scanner model 3_130214" (Analtech, Newark, DE, USA, CA S/N 130214GS-700), and the areas integrated with the WINCATS-3 software (Analtech, Newark, DE, USA).

Phospholipids and cholesterol :

Phospholipids content was estimated by measuring phosphorous in the lipid using standard method of AOCS³¹. Cholesterol was estimated according to the standard method of Zlatkis *et al.*³².

Fatty acid composition :

Fatty acids present in the fish waste lipid were derivatized to their corresponding methyl-esters using 7% BF₃-methanol method²⁸. About 200 mg of sample oil was hydrolyzed with 0.5 N NaOH in methanol (50 ml) for 1 h at reflux temperature. Afterward, BF₃-methanol reagent (5 ml) was added and boiled for one minute, and then 2 ml of hexane was added and boiled for one more minute. After cooling, 15 ml of a saturated sodium chloride solution was added. The hexane solution of methyl-esters at the top was extracted and transferred into a test tube with anhydrous sodium sulfate. The dry hexane solution (1 µl) was injected directly in gas chromatograph (GLC – make : Agilent, model : 6890n), fitted with a DB-wax capillary column (30 m × 0.25 m i.d.) and a FID detector. N₂, H₂ and airflow rate were maintained at 1, 30 and 300 ml/min respectively. Inlet and detector temperature was kept at 250 °C and the oven temperature was programmed as 150°–190°–230 °C an increment rate of 15 °C/min and 4 °C/min respectively and hold for 5 min and 10 min respectively. Quantitative data were corrected for differences in detector responses through analysis of authentic standards of each reported fatty acid.

Analysis of total mercury and arsenic content :

Total mercury and arsenic concentrations in the samples were determined by standard ICP-MS method after mineralization of the samples with microwave assisted acid digestion. Heavy metal concentrations in these digest solutions were determined by ICP-MS (Agilent 7500c, Waldbronn, Germany).

Statistical analysis :

The data were expressed as mean ±S.D. For all determinations, six replicates were carried out for both *C. catla* and *L. rohita*. All analyses were carried out in triplicate. A one-way ANOVA was also used for statistical analysis between *C. catla* and *L. rohita*. The *F* ratio of one-way ANOVA is significant when the *P* value <

0.05. The statistical program was Minitab release 13.31 (Minitab, State College, PA).

Conclusions :

The effective utilisation of the fishery by-products is of one of the foremost concern for increasing the economic effectiveness of fishery industries. The present study showed that the waste matter produced from *C. catla* and *L. rohita*, two highest consumed fish, could be considered as a new source of healthful lipid due to its high oil content and its fatty acid composition. An important aspect of these lipids is their higher carotene content, an important antioxidant component and lower concentration of toxic heavy metal. Due to presence of significant amount of essential fatty acids both in *C. catla* and *L. rohita* and good n-3/n-6 ratios the lipid will be suitable for human or aquaculture use. Therefore the increasing demand of healthful lipids can be partly addressed by these two lipids obtained from fish waste.

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